

Viscosity and Molecular Association.

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Attempts have been made from time to time to use viscosity data for elucidating the molecular association in the case of liquids. The most successful method used so far has been Bingham's fluidity method (Bingham and Harrison, *Z. physikal Chem.*, 1909, **66**, 1; Bingham, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, **43**, 287; Turner, "Molecular Association," 1915, p. 78) in which Bingham compares the calculated and observed temperatures for a given fluidity (inverse of viscosity) usually 200 or 300 and finds out molecular association by dividing the observed temperature by the calculated temperature. He calculates the temperature at which the given fluidity is attained by assigning definite temperatures to every element and every kind of linkage for the given fluidity and assuming that the temperature at which the compound reaches the fluidity is the sum of the temperatures corresponding to the various atoms and linkages in the molecule. The method gives quite good results but there is no theory behind it. During the last few years much work has been done on the viscosity of liquids. Now we know definitely that the viscosity changes with temperature in the case of unassociated liquids can be represented by the formula,

$$\log \eta = a + \beta/T$$

where η denotes viscosity, T absolute temperature and a and β two constants (Raman, *Nature*, 1923, **111**, 532; Dunn, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1925, **22**, 401; Andrade, *Nature*, 1930, **125**, 309; Sheppard, *Nature*, 1930, **125**, 489; Prasad, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, **10**, 143). This can be used for elucidating the molecular association of liquids as will be evident from what follows.

In the case of unassociated liquids since, $\log \eta = \left(a + \frac{\beta}{T} \right) / \frac{\delta \log \eta}{\delta \left(\frac{1}{T} \right)}$

which is equal to β , is constant whereas in the case of associated liquids it goes on decreasing with temperature, if the higher molecules break up into smaller ones. The author (*loc. cit.*) has shown that β generally increases with molecular weight. In the homologous series, β increases by about eighty for every increase in the molecule by C_2H_4 (*ibid.*) in the case of unassociated liquids. However it is not entirely a

function of molecular weight for the β values of normal and isohydrocarbons differ by as much as 4% at times. When two or more simple molecules form an associated molecule the arrangement of the atoms in the molecule is not disturbed except when they combine irreversibly forming entirely different kinds of molecules, *e. g.*, the condensation of acetylene to benzene. The molecules in the case of associated liquids combine by weak co-valent linkages which are disrupted when the temperature is raised. When the difference between the β values of normal and isohydrocarbons hardly exceeds 4%, we can safely assume that these weak co-valency linkages which exist between the molecules of a liquid forming associated molecules, will not alter the value of β except by increasing the average molecular weight. So it follows that

$$\frac{d \log \eta}{d \left(\frac{1}{T} \right)} \bigg/ T_1 \bigg/ \frac{d \log \eta}{d \left(\frac{1}{T} \right)} \bigg/ T_2 = \frac{M_1}{M_2}$$
 where M_1 and M_2 are the average molecular weights of the liquid at the temperatures T_1 and T_2 . From the above it is evident that by knowing the value of

$d \log \eta \bigg/ d \left(\frac{1}{T} \right)$ for a number of temperatures in the case of any liquid, the molecular association for all other temperatures can be calculated in terms of the molecular weight at one definite temperature.

In Figure 1 $\log \eta$ is plotted against $1/T$ for water, methyl alcohol, ethyl alcohol, propyl alcohol, butyl alcohol, formic acid and acetic acid.

TABLE I.

Liquids.	5°	25°	45°	65°	85°
Water	1041	870	763	680	636
Methyl alcohol	546	546	546	...	...
Ethyl alcohol	723	723	723	723	...
Propyl alcohol	946	946	946	946	946
Butyl alcohol	1009	1009	1009	1009	1009
Formic acid	...	774	725	655	655
Acetic acid	...	578	578	578	578

In Table I the values of $d \log \eta \bigg/ d \left(\frac{1}{T} \right)$ calculated from the figure for above liquids at a number of temperatures are given.

FIG. 1.

To illustrate how the molecular association at any temperature can be calculated in terms of the molecular weight at another temperature,

let us take the case of water. For water

$$\frac{\frac{d \log \eta}{d \left(\frac{1}{T}\right)} / 5^\circ}{\frac{d \log \eta}{d \left(\frac{1}{T}\right)} / 85^\circ} = \frac{1041}{636}$$

i.e., 1.6. So water at 5° is 1.6 times more associated on an average than at 85°. The constant value of β within any temperature range does not necessarily mean that the liquid is unassociated. All it means is that molecular association is not appreciably changing within this temperature range.

In order to find out the absolute value for molecular association, a method can be developed on the following lines.

The author has shown (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 10, 135) that $T_c/B = 0.7$ (approx.) for an associated liquid when T_c denotes critical temperature on the absolute scale. If critical temperature is known we can approximately find out the value of β for any liquid. We can apply this to the associated liquids also and the values obtained will refer to the unassociated molecules, since much below the critical temperature even the associated liquids cease to be associated. From

what has been said before $\frac{d \text{Log } \eta}{d \left(\frac{1}{T} \right)} / \beta$ (determined from T_c) will be

a measure of molecular association for the liquid at temperature T .

In Table II molecular association determined by this method is given. For the sake of comparison, the values determined by Eötvos-Ramsay method are also given.

TABLE II.

Liquids.	T_c°	β	t°	$\frac{d \log \eta}{d \left(\frac{1}{T} \right)}$	x degree of molecular association.	x from Eötvos- Ramsay method.	
Water	...	640	448	5°	1041	2.3	2.9
"	...	...	...	25	870	1.9	2.3
"	...	...	...	45	763	1.7	2.7
"	...	...	...	65	680	1.5	2.6
Methyl alcohol	...	508	356	0.60	546	1.5	3.6
Ethyl alcohol	...	517	332	0.70	723	2.0	3.0
Propyl alcohol	...	547	383	0.90	946	2.5	2.1
Butyl alcohol	...	560	392	0.110	1009	2.5	...
Acetic acid	...	595	416	20.110	578	1.4	2.0

A glance at the values of molecular association determined by the two methods will show that the values do not always agree. In the

case of water, surface tension method shows that the molecular association first increases and then decreases with temperature, whereas by this method we find a continuous decrease with temperature. In case of methyl alcohol, the value of molecular association from surface tension measurements is found to be 3.61, greater than that of water even — a fact which seems to be highly improbable considering that the boiling point of water is 35° greater than that of methyl alcohol in spite of the latter's higher molecular formula. By this method the molecular association is approximately 1.5 less than the molecular association of water. The most serious discrepancy is that the order of liquids arranged in descending order of molecular complexity is not found to be the same by the two methods. By the surface tension method we get a lower and lower value for molecular association in a homologous series as the molecular weight increases till we get absurd results sometimes, *e.g.*, the molecular association in the case of stearic acid is found to be one half. By this method in the case of alcohols the molecular association seems to be increasing with the molecular weight, a fact which is very doubtful. This may partly be due to the approximate nature of the two assumptions (a) $\beta/T_0 = 0.7$ and

$$\frac{d \log \eta / d \left(\frac{1}{T} \right)^+}{T_1} \bigg/ \frac{d \log \eta / d \left(\frac{1}{T} \right)}{T_2} = \frac{M_1}{M_2}$$

We can get some idea of the error involved by the following considerations.

The author has shown (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 10, 135) that β/T_B (where T_B denotes the boiling point of liquids) varies from 1.04 to 1.24 in the case of nineteen liquids. From this we might expect that β/T_0 would vary from 0.62 to 3.74. In the cases of eight liquids, β/T_0 has been calculated in the same paper and is found to be within this limit. Further as $T_B/T_0 = 0.6$ is only approximately true, we might expect a little more variation in the values of β/T_0 . β/T_0 for such varied liquids as bromine, ethyl ether, ethyl propyl ether, chloroform, allyl chloride, methyl sulphide and heptane₂ (not included in the above list) is also approximately equal to 0.7. From all this we can safely assume that it may fluctuate from 0.6 to 0.8 at the utmost in the case of unassociated liquids. Hence the maximum error involved in the calculation of β/T_0 will be 14%. As the difference in the β values of normal and isocompounds, where the structural difference is greater than between the associated and unassociated liquids, is about 4% at the utmost so

we may assume that the maximum error involved in the assumption

$$\frac{d \log \eta / d \left(\frac{1}{T} \right)}{T_1} / \frac{d \log \eta / d \left(\frac{1}{T} \right)}{T_2} = \frac{M_1}{M_2} \text{ will be about 4\%.}$$

The maximum and minimum possible values of the molecular association in the cases of methyl, ethyl, propyl and butyl alcohols as calculated by the author are given in Table III.

TABLE III.

Alcohols.	Maximum value of (x).	Minimum value of (x).
Methyl	1.9	1.1
Ethyl	2.4	1.6
Propyl	3.1	1.9
Butyl	3.1	1.9

If we accept the maximum value in the case of methyl alcohol, and minimum value in case of other alcohols, the molecular association seems to be least in the case of ethyl alcohol, whereas it should be least in the case of butyl alcohols. One explanation for this discrepancy might be that the assumptions of the author are less accurate than what he thinks. It might be also due to some error in the accepted values of the critical temperatures of the various alcohols as it seems rather surprising that the critical temperature of methyl and ethyl alcohols should be nearly the same. All the data have been taken from Bornstein-Landolt's tables.

SUMMARY.

1. The value of β for associated liquids corresponding to the unassociated state is calculated from the approximate relationship, $\beta/T_c = 0.7$.

2. The molecular association (x) at any temperature is calculated

from the formula, $x = \frac{d \log \eta / d \left(\frac{1}{T} \right)}{\beta}$.